

Kinetics of Benzene Hydrogenation on Iron - Zeolite Catalyst

ASHUTOSH RASTOGI

EG & G WASC, INC, P.O. Box 880, Morgantown, WV 26507, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 9 February 1987, revised 21 September 1987, accepted 23 August 1988

The hydrogenation of benzene over highly dispersed iron-zeolite catalyst was studied in the temperature range 80–160°, hydrogen partial pressures 149–805 torr and benzene partial pressures upto 45.5 torr, in a fixed bed, plug-flow reactor at a total pressure just above atmospheric. The amount of hydrogenated product cyclohexane formed was an indication of the catalyst activity. A kinetic rate equation of the form

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k^1 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_6][\text{H}_2]^3}{(1 + K_B^2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_6]^{0.5})^2}$$

fit the data, thus suggesting that one molecule of adsorbed benzene reacts with three molecules of hydrogen, as the rate determining step. An Eley-Rideal mechanism substantiated the rate expression.

CONSIDERABLE attention has been given to the study of the hydrogenation of olefins and aromatics. The benzene reaction has been studied since it is the simple model reaction which can be used to characterise hydrogenation catalysts. An advantage in studying benzene hydrogenation is that it is a clean reaction, giving in general, cyclohexane as the sole product, unless elevated temperatures (above 623 K) are employed, when cracking and rearrangement into several products occur.

Research on benzene hydrogenation has been carried out on active metals such as nickel¹⁻⁶, platinum⁷ and other group VIII transition metal catalysts. Few studies have been made on iron^{8,9} which is an inexpensive metal. Hydrogen reaction orders are reported^{2-5,22} to lie between 0.3 and 3.0. The reported^{2,4,5,9,22} benzene reaction orders are in the range -1 to 0.3. Badilla-Ohlbaum *et al.*¹⁰ reported no inhibiting effects due to cyclohexane, however, some workers disagree^{2,3,9}. Activation energies below 458 K have been reported to be as high as 67 (Refs. 2, 9) and 94.2 kJ mol⁻¹ (Ref. 13), however most values^{8,10-12} fall between 41 and 58 kJ mol⁻¹ for supported catalysts. A maximum in the benzene hydrogenation rate has been reported around 43 K by several workers^{2,3,5,9-12}.

Many different mechanisms and kinetic equations have been proposed^{2,7,12,13,16,22}. Working with radio-tracers, Tetenyi and Barbenics⁷ and Candy and Fouilloux¹ found evidence of two types of chemisorbed benzene species on the surface which can be hydrogenated. One type is attributed to dissociative adsorption through dissociation of the carbon-hydrogen bonds of the benzene ring. The second species is believed to be a π -complex formed by single hydrocarbon-metal interaction. For example, van Meerten and Coenen¹⁷ proposed three possible mechanisms based on the work of Snagovskii⁴. Two of these have an adjustable rate-

determining step and the third consists of a series of slow steps.

While unsupported promoted iron is the catalyst used presently for the ammonia synthesis and Fischer-Tropsch reactions, few studies have been devoted to supported iron. Possible advantages of supported iron catalysts might be (i) higher activity per unit volume due to higher dispersion, (ii) better activity maintenance because various chemical states of iron could be stabilised and (iii) improved and selective catalytic properties as a consequence of metal-support interactions. Zeolite-Y was considered an ideal support which could help achieve highly dispersed iron.

The purpose of the present work was to prepare a highly dispersed supported iron catalyst and to study the conditions under which this catalyst can be active for the hydrogenation of benzene. Kinetic studies of the reaction under these conditions were carried out with other supportive techniques in an attempt to characterise the catalyst. An expression for the rate and the reaction mechanism has been proposed.

Experimental

Catalyst preparation: The zeolite supported iron catalyst was prepared in two stages. The first step required the preparation of Fe^{II}-Y¹⁸, and in the second step sodium borohydride reduction^{19,20} gave the final catalyst form.

Na-Y zeolite (Linde SK-40) (5.0 g) and concentrated HCl (2 drops) were added to deoxygenated distilled water (250 ml). The slurry was thoroughly deoxygenated by purging with nitrogen for several hours. A solution of water (250 ml), iron(II) sulphate (2.5 g) and concentrated HCl (3 drops) was deoxygenated by nitrogen purge. The solution was then mixed with the slurry and

stirred at ambient temperature for 12 h under a continuous stream of nitrogen. The solid was subsequently allowed to settle and the supernatant fluid was drawn off by suction. The zeolite was rinsed with small portions of deoxygenated water (250 ml) containing concentrated HCl (3 drops). The Fe^{II}-Y was finally dried in a fast nitrogen flow. Its composition is reported¹⁰ to be Fe_{1.3}Na_{0.4}(AlO₂)_{5.6}(SiO₂)_{1.96}.250 H₂O. The freshly prepared hydrated form is faintly blue-green. On being exposed to air it becomes orange-green.

Fe^{II}-Y (5.0 g) was suspended in deoxygenated distilled water (100 ml) and 0.5 M sodium borohydride (250 ml) was added to it gradually with stirring. pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7 by adding dilute H₂SO₄. The exothermic reaction with sodium borohydride took place below 20°. The resulting suspension was washed with distilled water and dried under nitrogen. The catalyst was reduced at 177° in flowing hydrogen which resulted in a black coloured material, probably Fe⁰-Y. It contained 4.5% iron by weight as calculated by neutron activation analysis.

Kinetic apparatus : The reaction train involved a benzene saturator, a condenser, a preheater, a fixed-bed differential reactor and a gas chromatograph. Benzene partial pressure was varied either by diluting the reactant stream with hydrogen downstream from the condenser or by varying the condenser temperature. Hydrogen partial pressure was varied by diluting the hydrogen stream with argon. Flow-rates were controlled by Brooks pneumatic flow controllers. Exit flow-rates were measured with a soap bubble flowmeter. The preheater was 1/8" coiled copper tubing and was enclosed in a furnace whose temperature was controlled by a Powerstat. The vertical reactor was a 5 mm i.d. pyrex glass U-tube which was also enclosed in a furnace. A thermocouple sealed into the reactor gave the temperature around the catalyst bed. The thermocouple arrangement controlled the exact temperature of the reactant stream at the catalyst bed. The catalyst samples rested on a coarse porous glass disc and weighed from 0.16 to 0.40 g. Low metal loadings avoided temperature gradients in the reactor and gas flow-rate across the bed was maintained within necessary limits to achieve differential conditions in the reactor. Catalyst activities are expressed as g-mol of cyclohexane produced per min per g of iron.

A gas sampling loop ensured that 20 microlitres of the products were analysed using a Varian Aerograph 1860-1 gas chromatograph equipped with a column (8' x 0.125" o.d.) packed with 15% polyethylene glycol 600 on Chromosorb. The column was maintained at 80°. The product peak areas were evaluated by a Hewlett - Packard 3380A integrator.

Catalyst characterisation : The prepared catalyst had a 4.5% iron loading by weight as determined by neutron activation analysis. Transmission electron microscopy micrographs showed that iron particles

on the catalyst surface were between 50 and 150 Å. Scanning electron microscopy of the catalyst surface detected 12.83% iron on the fresh sodium borohydride reduced catalyst and 13.82% iron on the surface of the spent catalyst. This indicated that iron migrates to the surface of the catalyst during reaction. Comparison of Na-Y and Fe-Y zeolite by X-ray diffraction showed the enlargement of the lattice for the Fe-Y zeolite leading to the conclusion that some iron was present in the zeolite cages of the catalyst.

Results and Discussion

In a series of initial experiments it was established that supported iron had to be present in the zero oxidation state for the hydrogenation of benzene and higher oxidation states of the metal rendered the catalyst inactive. The catalysts prepared by reduction of Fe^{II}-Y by sodium borohydride exhibited substantial sustainable activity. A kinetic study of benzene hydrogenation over these catalysts was undertaken.

The gas phase reaction of benzene hydrogenation was studied at 80-160°, hydrogen partial pressure from 149 to 805 torr and benzene partial pressures up to 45.5 torr, in a differential plug-flow microreactor at a total pressure just above atmosphere. The reaction yielded cyclohexane and trace quantities of low molecular weight cracked hydrocarbons and methylcyclopentane. The amount of cyclohexane formed was a measure of the catalyst activity.

It was observed that benzene accumulated in the pores of the zeolite as shown in Fig. 1. The initial period of accumulation was a function of the inlet concentration of benzene. The amount accumulated was dependent on the catalyst temperature. Assuming that liquid benzene accumulated in the zeolite pores, it was calculated that approximately 35.9-52.7% of the pore volume was filled as the

Fig. 1. Accumulation of benzene in the zeolite pores at (□) 157° and (○) 90°.

temperature varied from 157 to 98°. Assuming that benzene is adsorbed in the supercages of the zeolite Y, it was calculated that 4.3 molecules at 98°, 3.6 molecules at 120° and 2.9 molecules at 157° were adsorbed per supercage of the zeolite catalyst. Since benzene has a high heat of adsorption on the Na-Y zeolite, this hold-up is not unexpected²¹.

Fig. 2 reveals that the activity of the catalyst varied with time. All runs exhibited an initial activation period during which the activity rose rapidly. After the activation period, the activity rose gradually and levelled within a 24 h period. The activity would then stay at this level or decay

Fig. 2. Catalyst activity varying with time at (□) 120° and (○) 92°.

very slowly for several weeks. Regenerations were done with fast flowing hydrogen for 4–8 h at room temperature. The possible reason for the initial peak is that the cyclohexane formed remains adsorbed in the pores of the catalyst until it suddenly desorbs. However, this phenomenon takes place only once in the entire duration of the run. It might be that in the freshly reduced catalyst all the metal atoms or ensembles are active and after an initial adsorption of benzene and desorption of cyclohexane, most of the metal sites become passive. Results from scanning electron microscopy showed that the surface iron content increased during the reaction which could be the possible reason for the gradual increase in activity with time.

Effect of benzene partial pressure on the rate : A series of experiments were performed at different temperatures in which the partial pressure of benzene in the feed was varied, keeping the total pressure constant. The results are shown in Fig. 3. Log rate versus log benzene concentration indicated that the benzene reaction order increased from -0.02 to 0.126 with temperature varying from 80 to 100°. At 80° the slightly negative benzene reaction order of -0.02 indicated that below the boiling

Fig. 3. Effect of benzene partial pressure on the rate at (□) 80°, (○) 120°, (Δ) 140° and (+) 160°.

point of benzene the rate-determining step is probably diffusion through the liquid benzene layer. Another series of experiments were performed at different benzene partial pressures where the effect of temperature on the rate was observed (Fig. 4). The rate of hydrogenation increased with temperature with the maximum observed at 150–160°. This may be compared to the value of 180° reported by several workers^{2,3,5,6,8,14–16}.

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on the rate at different benzene concentrations: (□) 5.72, (○) 9.21, (Δ) 14.50 and (+) 45.83 torr.

Since the benzene accumulation in the zeolite pores decreases with temperature, at some point this marked decrease in surface coverage is severe enough to decrease the overall rate. Since the maximum was observed with both ascending and descending temperatures it cannot be due to poisoning. Also this maximum is not due to thermodynamic limitations, as benzene conversion

at 473 K at these conditions is above 99%. These points are also made by Yoon and Vannice²².

Effect of hydrogen partial pressure on the rate : Experiments were performed at different hydrogen partial pressures, keeping the benzene partial pressure and the temperature constant. Fig. 5 shows a strong dependence of the hydrogenation rate on the partial pressure of hydrogen. Hydrogen reaction orders increase from 1.14 at 80° to 1.5 at 160°.

Fig. 5. Effect of hydrogen partial pressure on the rate at (□) 80°, (○) 100°, (Δ) 120°, (+) 140° and (×) 160°.

In another set of experiments, the effect of temperature on the rate was studied at various hydrogen partial pressures keeping the benzene partial pressure constant. The results are presented in Fig. 6. It is seen that the rate increases with both temperature and hydrogen partial pressure.

Fig. 6. Effect of temperature on the rates at different hydrogen concentrations : (□) 149.5, (○) 633.4 and (Δ) 760 torr.

Effect of cyclohexane partial pressure on the rate : Experiments were performed at different cyclohexane partial pressures keeping the hydrogen and benzene partial pressures constant. Cyclohexane had no effect on the hydrogenation rate, indicating that the desorption of the product is not rate-controlling. To calculate an approximate activation energy for the supported iron catalyst, a simple power rate law with benzene reaction order as 0.12 and hydrogen reaction order of 1.4 was assumed. A plot of $\ln k$ versus inverse temperature (Fig. 7) yielded an activation energy of 21.1 kJ mol⁻¹.

Fig. 7. Plots of $\ln k$ vs inverse temperature.

Plausible rate equation : An equation of the form,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k' [C_6H_6][H_2]^2}{(1 + K_B^2)^2 [C_6H_6]^{0.5}}$$

matched the experimental results with a correlation factor of above 0.999 and with a standard error of less than 0.1. The constants of the rate expression were determined by regression analysis.

The slope of $\ln k'$ versus inverse temperature (Fig. 8) gave a summed activation energy of 114.6 kJ mol⁻¹. From the slope of $\ln K_B$ versus $1/T$ (Fig. 9), the enthalpy of adsorption was calculated to be 122.1 kJ mol⁻¹. This is higher than the reported value¹⁶ of 29 kJ mol⁻¹ and an average value²³ of 95 kJ mol⁻¹ presumably because of the high heat of adsorption of benzene on zeolite²¹.

Reaction mechanism : Some of the conclusions reached from the experimental observations are summarised as follows. (i) At constant temperature and hydrogen partial pressure, the rate of benzene hydrogenation rises very rapidly with benzene concentration before reaching a plateau. This phenomenon suggests that the benzene adsorbs on the active sites till all the sites are filled so that an increase in the benzene partial pressure does not

Fig. 8. Plots of $\ln k'$ vs inverse temperature.

Fig. 9. Plots of $\ln K_B$ vs inverse temperature.

affect the rate. (ii) The rate of benzene hydrogenation is proportional to the hydrogen concentration at constant temperature and benzene partial pressure. There is no maxima or a constant hydrogenation rate in the range of hydrogen partial pressures studied suggesting that hydrogen reacts by collision. (iii) For constant partial pressures of benzene and hydrogen, the rate increases with temperature upto a maximum of $150-60^\circ$.

An Eley-Rideal mechanism is proposed which assumes that benzene adsorbs associatively on the surface via an intermediate species X. The structure of X is unknown as the interaction of benzene with the active sites present in the zeolite cages is not fully understood. The following set of reactions are proposed as the chemical steps in the hydrogenation of benzene.

(i) Chemisorption of benzene on a surface site via an intermediate species :

(ii) Reaction of adsorbed benzene with gaseous hydrogen :

(iii) Desorption of cyclohexane :

When the reaction of adsorbed benzene with hydrogen in the gas phase in rate-controlling and irreversible, the overall rate of hydrogenation yields an expression which is of the same form as the proposed rate equation. Limitations of postulating a reaction mechanism on the basis of kinetic studies are known. However, the presented mechanism and the derived rate expression give a reasonable explanation of the phenomenon and a very good interpretation of the data, whereas a simple power rate equation could not reproduce the experimental information over the whole range of conditions covered.

Although Langmuir-Hinshelwood type of mechanism have been generally proposed for non-supported metal catalysts, various experimental trends suggest an Eley-Rideal type of mechanism for the hydrogenation of benzene over iron-zeolite catalysts.

References

1. J. P. CANDY and P. FOUILLOUX, *J. Catal.*, 1976, **35**, 110.
2. J. E. GERMAIN, R. MAUREL, Y. BOURGROIS and R. SINN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, **60**, 1219.
3. O. HERBO, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1941, **50**, 257.
4. Y. S. SNAGOVSKII, G. O. LYUBARSKII and G. M. OSTROVSKII, *Kinet. Catal. (USSR)*, 1966, **7**, 232.
5. R. Z. C. VAN MEERTEN and J. W. E. COENEN, *J. Catal.*, 1975, **37**, 37.
6. H. A. FRANCO and M. J. PHILLIPS, *J. Catal.*, 1980, **63**, 346.
7. P. TETENYI and L. BARBENICS, *J. Catal.*, 1967, **8**, 215.
8. J. NICOLAI, R. MARTIN and J. O. JUNGERS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1948, **57**, 555.
9. K. P. RORTHE, A. RORTHE, B. ROSAHL and D. GELBIN, *Chem. Ing. Tech.*, 1970, **42**, 805.
10. N. E. ZLOTINA and S. L. KIPERMAN, *Kinet. Catal.*, 1967, **8**, 337, 1129.
11. G. O. BOND, "Catalysis by Metals", Academic, New York, 1962.
12. M. POLANYI and R. K. GREENHALGH, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, **35**, 520.
13. L. N. CANJAR and F. S. MANNING, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1962, **12**, 73.
14. O. HERBO and V. HAUCHARD, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1948, **52**, 35.
15. O. HERBO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **47**, 454.

RASTOGI : KINETICS OF BENZENE HYDROGENATION ON IRON-ZEOLITE CATALYST

16. R. BADILLA-OHLBAUM, H. J. NEUBURG, W. F. GRAYDON and M. J. PHILLIPS, *J. Catal.*, 1968, **12**, 228.
17. R. Z. C. VAN MEERTEN and J. W. E. COENEN, *J. Catal.*, 1977, **46**, 13.
18. J. R. PEARCE, W. J. MORTIER, J. B. UYTTERHOEVEN and J. H. LUNSFORD, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1981, **77**, 937.
19. V. N. ROMANNIKOV, K. G. IONE, I. A. OVSYANNIKOVA, E. M. MOROZ and S. V. BOGDANOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1980, **10**, 2241.
20. J. B. LEE, *J. Catal.*, 1981, **68**, 27.
21. D. W. BRECK, "Zeolite Molecular Sieves—Structure, Chemistry and Use", Wiley, New York, 1974.
22. K. J. YOON and M. A. VANNICH, *J. Catal.*, 1988, **82**, 457.